

THE CURRENT STATE OF MUSIC EDUCATION AND EXISTING PROBLEMS IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' NATIONAL MUSIC LISTENING SKILLS.

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the current state of music education in the formation of national music listening skills in secondary schools, problems in the formation of music listening skills and their solutions.

Keywords: school, student, culture, music, national, tradition, problem, solution, issue, youth, modern education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada umumta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarda milliy musiqani tinglash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda musiqa ta'limning hozirgi holati, musiqa tinglash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdagi muammolar va ularning yechimi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktab, o'quvchi, madaniyat, musiqa, milliy, an'ana, muammo, yechim, masala, yoshlar, zamonaviy ta'lim.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о современном состоянии музыкального образования в формировании навыков аудирования национальной музыки в общеобразовательных школах, проблемах в формировании навыков аудирования музыки и их решениях.

Ключевые слова: школа, ученик, культура, музыка, национальная, традиция, проблема, решение, вопрос, молодежь, современное образование.

Implementation of comprehensive measures to raise the spiritual and educational level of our students, expand the fields of culture and art, study and develop our national and classical music heritage, and support representatives of the field the main goal is related to the development of the state during the independence of our country. [1] Various measures should be taken to achieve this goal. "Such events help to attract young students to the fields of culture, art and music, to create opportunities for them to gain interest and experience, to develop their creative work and creative ideas, and to adapt them to the representatives of the field".[2]

Part of these activities is to attract the interest of our young students, to allow them to work creatively and develop their creative ideas. Such events can

bring our students to the fields of culture, art and music, give them extra time to return home and do their creative work, help them develop their creative abilities. [3] These events allow the organization of cultural and art institutions, the use of various entertainment and information-educational technologies for young generations, to attract them to their creative work and to show them how to look at the field of representation. Other activities are to support industry representatives. As useful as these events are, they help ensure that you work with experienced industry representatives, representatives with the ability to discuss and respond, national security and legal experts, and other professionals.

In particular, Resolution No. PD-4038 signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev on November 28, "On approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, supporting the creators of Uzbekistan" [4] Ilhom Public Fund, Foundation for the Development of Culture and Art under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan [5], Union of Composers and Composers of Uzbekistan [6], State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan, Fergana Regional Institute of State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan branch was established [7]. This festival was established in order to present the national status art of Uzbekistan to the world, to demonstrate its history and its uniqueness, as well as to serve the development of the national status art.

Disappeared musicians from Uzbekistan and other countries, joint choirs and dances will take part in the festival. The festival provides an opportunity to get acquainted with the best examples of national status art, competitions, performers and performers. The purpose of the event is to increase the prestige of our unique heritage on a global scale, to implement the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to support and encourage the further development of theater and music in Uzbekistan" on issues of development on adding to the decision No. 415 of October 28, 1995 (Residence of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status" 2017 - Decision No. PD-3391 dated November 17), on approval of the regulations for equipping children's music and art schools with musical instruments, special furniture, equipment and other items [8], The decision "On approving the regulation on the procedure for paying and using fees for studying in horse schools" was an important practical step on the way. [9]

“In the past period, in the field of development of science and technology, necessary infrastructures for a number of types of education are being created, certain intellectual and technological potential is being formed”. In turn, experimental and innovative activities in the field of education are focused on the modernization of education and the development of new educational technologies and resources, their testing, and introduction to the educational process. [10]

However, there are systemic problems in the field of music education, insufficient attention is paid to the good use of existing opportunities and potentials for the development and implementation of innovative ideas and technologies, against the effective implementation of the intended reforms and the innovative development of music education in the field of science in the country. the constraints shown are important deadlines. Firstly, the lack of adequate analysis and study of the achievements and development trends of modern science and innovative technologies in music education; secondly, universities, research institutes and academies are usually of great importance for the independent development of the country. These institutes help to increase investments in innovative development and scientific research, as well as to strengthen distance education for researchers and students in this field.

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